

ISic0401

Candelabrum dedicated to Minerva

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

candelabrum

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Inventory notes found in 'podere di Rizza'; CIL observes in 1876 together with an aedicula

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 229

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 83 cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aius) · Marcius · Zoilus ·

2. Minervae ·

Apparatus

Text based upon inventory transcription, which notes interpuncts after every word

Translation (en)

Gaius Marcius Zoilus (dedicated this) to Minerva

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491612

EDCS 21900442

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7120 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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